

Problems of Working Women at Work Place

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Abstract

The problems and difficulties of working women at work place are multidimensional. Women workers at work place face the problems of low and discriminatory wage, exploitative working conditions, lack of secured employment, sexual harassment. Sexual harassment at the workplace affects the well being and economic livelihood of the women employee, while also affecting the moral productivity and integrity of the work place. Lack of awareness about the law and their rights is one of the fundamental causes behind the powerlessness, bias, and exploitation that women face at their work. In this an attempt is made to discuss the problem of women workers at work place.

Keywords Women Workers, Exploitation, Discrimination, Problems, Work Place, Social Security, Wages

Introduction

The condition of working women in India as well as in the entire world in general is considered to be very distressing. Working women in general are subject to discrimination at various levels. The problems and difficulties of working women are multi-dimensional, varying from woman to woman at personal level, and section to section at general level and hence need to be analyzed in depth.[1] There are very serious problems of wages, employment, income and standard of living and sexual harassment among working women. They are not able to get any advantage of social security schemes. Due to their ignorance and illiteracy they are not benefited from present welfare schemes.[2]

There has indeed been a growing realization that the women workers form an integral part of the process of national development. This has made the government make continuous effort to give women workers a better deal in spheres of work and to recognize their contribution to the socio-economic development of the Country. However, what has been done remains a drop in the ocean and the women worker remain exploited and unprotected.[3]

Objective of study

The objective of paper are

1. To know what problems faced by women workers at work place.
2. What is the reasons behind the problems of working women.

Review of Literature

There are many studies in India on Women Workers. This review of literature aims to show the need for the study of Problems of Women Workers at work place.

G.D. Gambhir in his study on "Labour in small scale industries in Madhya Pradesh with special reference to women and child labour in cotton ginning, bidi making and rice milling and shellac manufacture" found that wages of unskilled women workers ranged between 65% to 75% that of the unskilled men workers. Men coolies earn double that of women coolies.[4]

A study is conducted by *D.P. Singh* on “*Women workers in unorganised sector*” in 2005 as revealed that the availability of basic facilities like light, water, kitchen arrangements, toilets and washing facilities, etc. in the brick kilns industry are not satisfactory. Although water was made available to all respondents for washing, drinking and bathing, there was no proper arrangement for it in most of the brick kilns. Besides this, there were no proper and essential devices provided to them for their safety. For instance, the women who carry the dried bricks to the trench need to be provided with hand gloves for protecting their hands and fingers from bruises and injuries. Similarly those women who work as unloaders of the trench require gas masks, goggles because they work in the extreme dust all the time.

Main Text**PROBLEMS OF WORKING WOMEN**

Long working hours, conditions of work, wages, types of job and other situation is still not favourable to women workers. Women workers have many problems and problems of working women are more serious and server.

(i) Poor Health

Women universally have lower status and are seem only in their reproductive roles. Women anywhere in the world have to suffer from some in built disadvantages, compared to men, because of certain biological reasons. The law prohibits women employment in dangerous and heavy operations in organised sector as well as in unorganised sector. However, majority of them work in the unorganised sector and consequently, get hardly any benefits made by the provisions of the law. What the *Factories Act 1948* does say is that women must be prohibited from employment in dangerous and heavy operations. No women worker should be asked to clean or lubricate or adjust any machinery while it is in motion, if her work exposes her to the risk of injury from any moving part. No women workers should be employed for pressing cotton in any part of a factory in which a cotton opener is at work. There are also specified limits on the amount of weight a woman worker can carry. The state governments can, therefore, restrict or prohibit the employment of women in only operation which may expose them to serious risk of personal injury.

The Act also says that there should be separate toilets and sanitary dressing rooms for women workers. It specifies the need for keeping both clean. There is women workers' complaint of the absence or shortage of separate toilets at their work place. The fact is that the *Factories Acts* which are enforced by the factory inspectors are not implemented. Thus in different industries women workers are suffering from innumerable difficulties and nothing has been done to alleviate them.

It is well spread belied that the physical structure and maternal functions of women place her at a disadvantage. But practices do not follow this. Women have never shirked hard labour, whether it is farming, planting, transplanting, winnowing, weeding, harvesting, grinding, pounding, nothing holds them back. Male refusal to take on specific home and child-care responsibilities has also placed a dual responsibility of home as well as work place on working women. These responsibilities cause mental as well as physical problem which ultimately leads to health hazards.[5]

(A) Emotional Problems

Unemployment, underemployment and temporary work are more common among women than among men. As per available research, unemployment is harmful to health and constitutes a serious risk for the workers' emotional stability, because it leads to poverty, deteriorates self-image and self-esteem.

(B) Physical Health

A large number of women workers complain of frequent headaches, back pain, circulatory disorders, fatigue, and emotional and mental disorders.

There is adverse effect of work on the health of women workers, this is due to long hours of work, lifting weights, overburden, poor working conditions, lack of light, ventilation, water space etc. Thus, work related health problems from which women have been suffering is given here:

(a) Problems due to being in Contact with Hazardous Material

Constant contact with wood smoke while cooking dyes, cashew oil, chemicals and chemical fumes, tobacco dust, silica and other dust while mining, cotton dust, gases like carbon monoxide, formaldehyde, etc. give rise to a host of respiratory problems like shortness of breath, constant discomfort, byssinosis, tuberculosis, silicosis, cancer, etc.

Different chemicals, fumes and dust have affected women who do diverse types of work – housework, photocopying, electronics, mining, agriculture, building and construction. The effects on women's health have been disastrous with severe morbidity and also fatalities.

(b) Problems related to Women's Work Environment – Lack of Light, Ventilation, Water, Space etc.

Inadequate lighting, long working hours with extremely minute work like chicken embroidery, lace making, zari embroidery, tagai work, etc. cause severe problems like poor vision, eye-strain, and headaches.

(c) Problems Related to Lifting Weights

Women in building and construction, on Employment Guarantee Scheme work in brick kilns, women who have to carry water over long distances, often, while also carrying their children on their backs, have to constantly carry very heavy weights during all their working life-often from childhood to old age, also immediately before and after child birth. These give rise to health problems like menstrual disorders, prolapsed of the uterus, miscarriages, back problems, especially those related to spinal column, causing serious and long term repercussions.

(d) Problems Related to Long Hours of Work

Most of the serious health problems get aggravated due to the long hours of work women have to put in. The postural problem women face, in most of the work they do, get much worse, as women work for 8 to 14 hours each day.

(e) Problems Related to Mental Health

Women are known to have to work in at least two shift, if not three. They have to do or take the responsibility for almost all the household work, child care, caring for the old and sick as well as earning a living. In whatever way women try to combine these different equally strenuous roles, it gives rise to extreme mental strain.

Secondly, most women have to work in extremely insecure conditions. Socially too, women are extremely vulnerable. This exposes them to various forms of oppressions, including sexual harassment, wife beating, systematic violence, the sexual division of labour at home, in society and at the workplace and restrictions on the freedom of mobility.[6]

(ii) Wage Related Problems

Women works to increase the income of the family or widow works for self dependence. Number of women working only for hobby or to get an employment is very less in India. Thus wage rate they are getting is an important factor to be considered. Most significant problems of female labourers are problems relate to wages. Females get less as compared to males. It is unjust that a worker spends many hours at difficult work and does not even earn enough to feed himself and

her family.[7] There have been quite a few micro-studies that show that women workers in unorganised sector invariably get paid much less than men.

Only 7 percent of the Country's female workforce is employed in the organised sector. The organised sector comprises units registered under the Factories Act of 1948 and covers those using power and employing ten or more workers, as well as units not using power but employing 20 or more workers. In addition the organised sector is governed by legislation such as *the Minimum Wages Act, Labour Welfare Regulations, and Contract Labour (Regulation and Abolition) Act*. Strictly speaking violations of those Acts can be challenged in a Court of Law.

Even in the public sector, where employment has gone up substantially, a large proportion of women are shunted into low paid jobs. At every level of work, they are paid lower wages defeating the constitutional position of equal pay for equal work for both men and women. Wage discrimination is problem all over the world, especially in the third world countries, where the process of industrialization is still going on.[8]

(iii) Lack of Social Security

Social security still eludes most workers in the informal sector, especially women workers. In the unorganised the concept, more so its practice, is hardly applicable or observed consistently or categorically and the framework and thrust seldom satisfy the nature of work and plight of workers. For the women component those protective provisions may be most urgent but they are either not-existent or being flagrantly flouted.

Recently, the *Unorganised Workers' Social Security Act 2008* has been passed. The Act contemplates the delivery of benefits to unorganised workers in instances of sickness, disability, maternity, unemployment, old age and the death of a family's breadwinner. Despite of these laudable achievements, women workers have no social security benefits. Registration is necessary to get the benefits under this Act. There may also be difficulties in registering the workers on account of the suppression of facts by employers and contractors.

(iv) Absence of Child Care Facilities

Women working in the informal sector do not have any child-care facilities (crèches are absent or ill equipped even in the organised sector). Most often women workers, particularly in the informal sector, are forced to leave their children at home, under the care of their elder children, or old people or neighbours.[9]

In fact crèche facility is non-existent in all most all small-scale industries. The common causes are: these factories, which are seasonal in nature do not come under the ambit of the legal provision. Lack of space for implementing the provision is also cited as one impediment. Employers also deliberately avoid recruiting or engaging married one or women with infants for escaping shouldering of extra bit of expense. Lack of knowledge about the applicability of this very provision and absence of bargaining power to force employer to provide the facility are few other reasons.[10]

(v) Home-Based Work

Home-Based work is considered more productive as it paves the way for the term "flexible work" responsibilities. Despite increased recognition at the policy level of the contribution of the home-based sector to the overall economy, home based workers largely remain invisible in data and statistics and are deprived of access to any form of organizational support, wage protection or employment benefits.

(vi) Gender Discrimination

Gender refers to how biological differences between men and women work in social spheres. At economic plain, gender appears as sexual division of labour where some types of work are related to men and women separately. In broader sense, production is men's and reproduction women's.

Gender inequalities in various forms pervade all operations / activities in which women are engaged. The division of labour is highly sex segregated and biased. Skilled and higher wage earning jobs are male preserve and arduous/ unskilled of women's. Even when both males and women are doing the same type of work, women in general get about 30 percent less wage.[11] Discrimination is manifest at every stage of employment, from recruitment to remuneration, occupational segregation and at time of lay-off.

The Indian Judiciary to a certain extent has taken lead in securing socio-economic justice to women. The creative thinking that is evident in cases like *Kishori Mohanlal Bakshi v. Union of India*[12], *C.B. Muthamma v. Union of India*, [13] *Air India v. Nargeesh Meerza*[14], *People's Union for Democratic Rights v. Union of India*[15], *Randhir Singh v. Union of India*[16] is a good sign of Judicial activism. The Court rightly maintained that women are the participants in the mainstream and deserve equal treatment. Old laws making women's biology as a basis of segregation are unreasonable and the Supreme Court has held such laws unconstitutional. The Supreme Court has interestingly maintained recently that giving preference to women in jobs was only an affirmative action and need not be deemed as reservation. In spite of the judiciary efforts, gender discrimination has been seen everywhere.

(vii) Poor Living and Working Conditions

Despite the fact that many labour legislations have been made applicable to the unorganised industry the living and working conditions of the workers in these industry are highly unsatisfactory and welfare amenities actually available to them are just negligible. Women workers are the worst sufferers as their employment is regarded as secondary to that of male workers. Special provisions regarding the protection and welfare of women workers are either not at all enforced or they do not exist in the labour laws applicable to the industry. They have to work under very poor working and living conditions. Women workers have poor bargaining power that is why they cannot pressurize the employers for their rights, which leads to this exploitation. The living conditions of the workers in unorganised sector are observed to be quite unsatisfactory. It is because besides bad conditions of their quarters, these workers have also not been provided with proper facilities of drinking water, sanitation, health and education..

Workers engaged in building and construction industry have invariably to handle dusty, hard or rough material like sand, cement, concrete bricks, etc. They were thus prone to injuries and health hazards. No precautions have been taken by the employer to prevent inhalation of dust fumes etc..

(viii) Occupational hazards and Accident

There is danger of accident during the working of workers. For, in most of the cases, machine is responsible. Labourers in construction sector have dangers of breakdown of building or slab collapse and other accidents. The risk involved in construction work is very high particularly for women workers, who have to climb great heights carrying heavy loads. Most of the workers engaged in various industries suffer from certain occupational diseases due to bad working environment and unsuitable working conditions. The most common occupational diseases are Asthma, T.B. and Silicosis. No compensation is provided to the workers, under the provision of workmen's compensation Act, who contract such diseases.

(ix) Sexual Harassment

Sexual harassment is another serious hazard faced by working women. Whether in the organised or unorganised sector, whether illiterate, low paid workers or highly educated and highly paid executives, a large number of working women face sexual harassment at the workplace.

Sexual harassment includes such unwelcome sexually determined behaviour such as physical contacts and advances, sexually coloured remarks, showing pornography and sexual demands, whether by words or actions.[17] It includes anything from a remark to a physical advance that offends the self respect of a women. Sexual behaviour may be considered sexual harassment when person finds himself personally, offensive sexually. Such behaviour may be subtle or obvious, verbal or non-verbal.

Women's groups all over India have led numerous campaigns against sexual harassment, eventually bringing the issue to the attention of the Supreme Court in 1997.[18] In 1997 the Supreme Court recognized sexual harassment at the workplace as a violation of human rights. The Supreme Court in *Vishaka v. State of Rajasthan*[19] issued guidelines and norms for due observance at all work places or other institutions to avoid sexual harassment of the women. Such efforts notwithstanding, the attitudes that promote sexual harassment remain prevalent. The Supreme Court's legally binding guidelines for employers have hardly been implemented in practice.

The Sexual Harassment of Women at Workplace (Prevention, Prohibition and Redressal) Act, 2013, is a landmark Indian legislation aimed at protecting women from sexual harassment at their workplaces and establishing mechanisms for redressal of complaints. It defines sexual harassment and mandates the formation of Internal Complaints Committees (ICCs) in organizations with 10 or more employees to handle such complaints.

Sexual harassment at the workplace affects the well being and economic livelihood of the woman employee, while also affecting the moral productivity and integrity of the workplace.[20] It is submitted that sexual harassment of women at the workplace is not a purely legal problem. It is a socio-legal problem and therefore, a purely legal solution will not help. Social awareness of the existence of sexual harassment at the workplace should be raised. Women should be encouraged to come out with the problems that they face at the workplace but at the same time care should be taken to ensure that the plea of sexual harassment is not taken to settle personal scores

Conclusion

After going through all these details, it is observed that problems and difficulties of working women are multidimensional. Women workers at workplace face the problems of low and discriminatory wage, exploitative working conditions, lack of secured employment, sexual harassment. They are to operate in a vicious circle of deprivation, denigration and subsistence struggle. Women workers have to face instability and insecurity of employment, non-observance of labour regulations enjoined by enactments. Lack of awareness is one of the fundamental causes behind the powerlessness, bias and exploitation that women face at their work.

Suggestions for the future Study 1. Women workers need to be made aware about their interests, various legislative provisions and authorities for protection against discrimination, sexual harassment and strategies for grievance redressal. They should be motivated to utilize the government programmes for their socio-economic development.

2. NGOs, particularly those engaged in the activities of women's welfare, have an important role to play in being on the forefront in awareness generation and empowering women to solve their problems.

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